

Kinetic Evidence for Steric Enhancement of Resonance from Ethylation of Phenols**

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The rates of ethylation of some mono and disubstituted sodium phenoxides with ethyl iodide at 30° have been determined. The 3-methyl group in sodium 4-methoxy-3-methyl-phenoxide or the halogeno group in sodium 4-methoxy-3-halogenophenoxide does not sterically inhibit the resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the aromatic ring but enhances it. The kinetic data obtained in the present study provides additional evidence for the concept of steric enhancement of resonance.

THE phenomenon of steric enhancement of resonance was first reported by Baliah and Uma¹ while studying the electric dipole moments of some substituted nitroanisoles and methoxyacetophenones. The studies of diamagnetic susceptibility measurements and kinetic studies of several trisubstituted benzenes (I) provided additional evidence in support of this view²⁻⁷. In the present paper the kinetic data for the reaction of substituted sodium phenoxides with ethyl iodide is used to substantiate the above phenomenon. The preferred orientation of the methoxy group and the consequent steric enhancement of resonance are possible only when there is a single group ortho to the methoxy group.

X=CH₃, Cl, Br, I

Y=COOEt, COCH₃, NO₂, NH₂, SOCH₃, CH(OH)CH₃

Experimental

The experimental procedure followed was similar to that of Goldsworthy⁸ with slight modifications. The reaction was followed at 30° and the solvent used for this study is absolute ethanol (twice dried and distilled over lime and then once with sodium). A 0.5 M sodium phenoxide solution was prepared by adding the calculated amount of phenol to a 0.5 M ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide.

A solution of ethyl iodide in ethanol (0.5 M) was also prepared and these two solutions were mixed. Titrations were carried out at suitable intervals of time

taking aliquots of the reaction mixture. The unchanged phenoxide was estimated using standard hydrochloric acid with methyl orange as indicator. The second order rate constants were calculated from the equation

$$k=1/t \cdot \frac{x}{a(a-x)} \text{ for this } S_N^2 \text{ reaction,}$$

For disubstituted phenoxides the indicator was of no use due to colour interference and hence a pH meter was used for this purpose.

Results and Discussion

The rate constants for the ethylation of some mono and disubstituted sodium phenoxides at 30° are given in Table 1. This S_N² reaction gets accelerated by electron donating groups in the benzene ring while the electron retard withdrawing substituents it. Sodium 4-methoxyphenoxide reacts almost 1.5 times faster than the unsubstituted sodium phenoxide, the electron-releasing methoxy group being responsible for this rate increase. The rate is still higher for sodium 4-methoxy-3-methylphenoxide (nearly two times). But this increase in rate does not seem solely due to the 3-methyl group because the observed rate constant for sodium 4-methoxy-3-methylphenoxide is 14.6 × 10⁻⁵ l mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹ whereas the calculated value is 13.3 × 10⁻⁵ l mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹ on the basis of additivity of group effects⁹. This significant difference in the rate arises because the 3-methyl group does not sterically inhibit the resonance interaction of the methoxy group with the aromatic ring but actually enhances it.

The enhanced electron release of the methoxyl in the transition state of 4-methoxy-3-methylphenoxide (II) compared to that in 4-methoxyphenoxide is, therefore,

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TABLE I—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE ETHYLATION OF SUBSTITUTED SODIUM PHENOXIDES WITH ETHYL IODIDE AT 30°

Substituents	Rate constants $k \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$		k_{obs}/k_{calc}
	Observed	Calculated	
H	7.54	—	
3-Methyl	8.93	—	
3-Chloro	5.40	—	
3-Bromo	5.80	—	
4-Methoxy	11.2	—	
3,5-Dimethyl	10.6	10.6	1.00
3-Methyl-4-methoxy	14.6	13.3	1.10
3-Chloro-4-methoxy	12.1	8.28	1.46
3-Bromo-4-methoxy	16.0	8.60	1.85

due to the combined electronic and steric effects of the adjacent methyl group. The methyl of the methoxy group seems to take an orientation *trans* to the

X = CH₃, Cl, Br

3-methyl increasing the probability of its attaining planarity with the aromatic ring due to restricted

rotation. Thus there can be enhanced resonance interaction of the -OMe group with the aromatic ring resulting in a greater electron-release to the phenoxy group. In addition to this, the observed rate constants for sodium 3-chloro-4-methoxyphenoxide and sodium 3-bromo-4-methoxyphenoxide are very much higher than the calculated ones. The ratio of k_{obs}/k_{calc} clearly indicates the extent to which this enhancement of resonance takes place with their increasing size. The observed rate of sodium 3,5-dimethylphenoxide is very close to the predicted value indicating the strict additivity of group effects.

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References

1. V. BALIAH and M. UMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1960, 21.
2. V. BALIAH and V. M. KANAGASABAPATHY, *Indian Chem.*, 1971, 9, 181.
3. JUDITH DAYANA, J. JEYANTHI, "Substituent and steric influence on the diamagnetic susceptibility of benzene derivatives", Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1975.
4. M. KRISHNA PILLAY and S. KANAGAVEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 368.
5. THEYMOLI BALASUBRAMANIAN, "Steric Enhancement of Resonance", Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1976.
6. P.V.V. SATYANARAYANA, "Kinetics of oxidation and reduction of aryl methyl sulphoxides", Ph.D. Thesis, Annamalai University, 1977.
7. V. BALIAH and V. SUNDARI, Private Communication.
8. J. GOLDSWORTHY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1254.
9. H. P. CROCKER and B. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1808.